

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-48-IG-10% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	21	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 48
Injection Volume:	1.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/29/2022 10:24:18 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 19:44:44 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.350	1748442	49.78	189674
2	8.043	1764115	50.22	141966

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-47-IG-10% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	20221029
Vial:	59	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	lm 4 47
Injection Volume:	1.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/29/2022 19:13:44 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 19:44:58 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.349	3584319	97.95	408913
2	8.362	75043	2.05	5860